

DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE BASED COMPARATIVE STUDY OF QUALITY OF WORK LIFE OF GOVERNMENT & PRIVATE ENGINEERING INSTITUTE FACULTIES FROM MAHARASHTRA STATE

MADHURI SITARAM BAN

Lecturer, Department of Applied Science, Government Polytechnic ,Aurangabad, M.S. India , madhuri_ban@rediffmail.com

DR. U. V. PANCHAL

Vice Principal and Head of Commerce Department, MSPm's Deogiri College, Aurangabad, M.S. India, vupanchal@outlook.com

ABSTRACT:

In this paper, we have compared and analyzed the difference between quality of work life between government & private engineering institute faculties. The demographic profile affect on the quality work life of both the faculties government & private. Weighted average mean & standard mean helps to understand satisfaction level of employees.

KEYWORDS: Demographic profile, Quality of Work Life, Maharashtra State Engineering Institutes, Standard Deviation.

INTRODUCTION:

Faculty members are one of the greatest resources in any society, who play a crucial role in training specialized forces. Ultimately, the result of their efforts is social development and growth in human capital. Imparting specialized knowledge is made possible by higher educational institutions only with the sincere efforts of the teaching faculty employed in these higher educational institutions. Passing on specialised knowledge to the student community can happen effectively only when the teaching staff are truly committed to their profession. As teachers understand the fact that teaching is a noble profession, they are to play a crucial role at all levels from primary to secondary and to the college level.

The responsibilities, roles, and expectations to be played by the college or university faculty member is greater. The teaching faculty to be an expert in the subjects, possessing an in depth knowledge about related fields of specialization, an embodiment of empathy, with high tolerance level and a technology savvy, and the list is infinitely big. Having such a great expectation about them from all quarters faculty members need to fulfill a lot of obligations. Thus, their contributions towards the successful implementation and execution of their work are very important. This can happen once the person involved feels that his expectations are taken care of by the management or the government. His level of satisfaction makes a big

difference in his contributions for the development or the growth of the institutions.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Quality of Work Life (QWL) has assumed increasing interest and importance in both industrialized as well as developing countries of the world. It has become critical in the last two decades because of the changed business environment and family structure (Akdere, 2006). According to Ganlinsky & Stein, (1990) the combination of fluctuating work environment with competing work and family commitments has negatively affect employees in many ways, such as lowered employee morale, reduced productivity and increased employee turnover employees.

Although most researches have been done on QWL, the majority of them have been focused on western settings. Only very few studies have been conducted in the Asian setting (Daud, 2008; Mat Zin, 2004; Saklani, 2004; Wyatt and Chay, 2000). Till today, the literature on QWL is widespread yet reasonably little work in this area relates to the field of higher education and still less on Indian higher learning institutions. The purpose of this study was to determine factors that can effectively represent the conception of a quality of work life in higher learning institutions in India.

METHODOLOGY:

To analyze and interpret the data with any suitable statistical tool is used out of Chi-square or ANNOVA.

DESCRIPTIVE CUM DIAGNOSTIC:

Descriptive study describes the agreement level of quality work life of the respondents, with respects to the various dimensions namely, Adequate and fair compensation, working conditions, opportunity to use and develop human capacities, opportunity for career growth, social integration in the work force constitutionalism respectively. Diagnostic study attempts to find out the association between selective socio-demographics characteristics. (Age, sex, department, experience, annual income, Educational qualification, type of family) and level of QWL perceived

by the respondents. Hence descriptive cum diagnostic research design was adopted.

In all over Maharashtra state there are 17 Government engineering and aided institutes and 300 Private engineering institutes. Out of these 17 Government engineering and aided institutes and 300 engineering institutes the researcher had choose 100 % of the Government engineering and aided institutes and 30 Private engineering institutes i.e. 17 +30=47 institutes from all over the universities in Maharashtra State.

Table1: Satisfaction Level of government engineering and private engineering faculties

Sr. No.	Characters	Details	Faculty Members		%
			Government Engineering	Private Engineering	
1	Gender	Male	113	135	43.6
		Female	150	170	56.4
		Below 30 Years	78	88	29.4
2	Age Group	30-35Years	96	111	36.4
		35-40Years	32	45	13.8
		Above 40 Years	55	61	20.4
3	Marital status	Married	198	223	74.4
		Single	68	77	25.6
4	Designation	Assistant Professor	221	270	86.4
		Associate Professor	31	37	12
		Professor	3	4	1.2
		Director	1	2	0.4
5	Educational Qualification	PG Only	189	197	68
		PG With SLET/NET	52	43	17
		PG, SLET/NET, Ph.D	39	46	15

Table 2: Satisfaction Percentage

Sr. No.	Particulars	Percentage
S1	Satisfied	71%
S2	Dissatisfied	21%
S3	No Opinion	8%
Total		100

People pay much more attention to their life style and the money they earn from the work than their predecessors. Employees. Expectations of a compensation plan are that it is fair and equitable, that it provides them with tangible rewards commensurate with their skills and, further, that it provides recognition and a livelihood. Job satisfaction is often achieved where performance is recognized by appropriate and equitable performance related pay supplemented with other perks, benefits and non-financial recognition and rewards, which meets the team member's expectation.

Table 3: Overall mean scores

Sr. No	Particular	Mean	Standard Deviation
S1	Job Satisfaction	3.0985	.98403
S2	General Wellbeing	2.9486	.85285
S3	Control at Work	2.9153	.89761
S4	Home Work Interface	2.9984	.68010

FINDINGS:

- Faculty members from government colleges have high satisfaction level regarding pay & benefits as compare to private engineering institutes.
- Regarding teaching and learning faculty members are satisfied with development of Teaching and Learning and use of modern teaching aids which has ranked first and second respectively, whereas the third and fourth rank goes to distinct teaching methodology and recognition of teaching accomplishment provides less satisfaction.

DISCUSSION:

Regular orientation/refresher courses, workshops, seminar, symposium etc. should be organized for teachers up gradation on current trends, methods, strategies, pedagogy of education.

Self Development is another important factor, lack of which causes of dissatisfaction. Provide enough privacy in their job, create sense of one community, encouraged to develop their new skills, provides social mobility, create clear set of goals and provide opportunities.

CONCLUSION:

In this paper we have discussed about the effect of demographic profile & job satisfaction level of faculties of government & private Engineering institute which should take up the initiative of improving and enhancing the emotional intelligence of their employees. This can be done by designing and providing effective training to their employees. This will help enhance the skills of the employees with regard to "self - awareness" self - awareness forms the most critical element of emotional intelligence. High self - awareness helps an individual to monitor the actions and try to rectify it if required, self-awareness guides an individual to fine tune the job performance style and become more acceptable and socially networked.

REFERENCES:

- 1) Ali, N. A and Zairi, M. (2005) *Service Quality in Higher education*, Bradford University School of Management. Bradford
- 2) Barnet. R, (1992), *Improving higher education: Total quality care*, Buckingham, SRHE&OU
- 3) Lachlan E.D Crawford and Paul Shutler, (1999) " *Total Quality Management in education: problems and issues for classroom teacher*", The International Journal of educational Management, Vol.1 pp.67-72
- 4) Herzberg, F., Mausner, B., and Snyderman, B. (1959), " *The Motivation to Work*" (2nd ed.) New York: John Wiley. Hian, C.C., and Einstein, W.O., (1990), " *Quality*

- of Work Life (QWL): What can unions do?* S.A.M. Advanced Management Journal, Vol. 55, No. 2, p. 17-22. Karasek, R.A. "Control in the Workplace and its Health-Related Aspects", in Sauter, S.L., Hurrell, J.J., Cooper, C.L. (Eds), Job Control and Worker Health, Wiley, New York, NY, pp.129-59, 1989
- 5) Sinha P, Sayeed OB. *Measuring Quality of Working Life : Development of an Inventory*. Indian Journal of Social Work. 41; 219-226, 1980.
- 6) Sirgy, J.M, Efraty,D., Siegel,P and Lee,J.D. *A New Measure of Quality of Work Life (QWL) based on need satisfaction and spillover* Social Indicators Research 55: 241-302, 2001.

IJRPET